

CP2K biomolecular QM/MM performance profiling

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Overview

This report, which forms part of BioExcel-2 project deliverable D1.6, summarises the analysis and visualisation of the absolute performance, parallel scaling, and subroutine-level profiling of CP2K (versions 8.1 and 8.2) when executing benchmarks taken from the BioExcel biomolecular QM/MM benchmark suite on different common HPC architectures. The results shown were used to help identify and prioritise CP2K optimisation work during the BioExcel-2 project.

The raw CP2K output logs used to generate the figures in this report are available from:

https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_results

Our analysis script used to generate the figures from the raw results is available from:

https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_script

Benchmarks

The benchmarks run are taken from the BioExcel QM/MM benchmark suite, which are available from and described in more detail in:

https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_suite

These benchmarks vary independently the number of QM atoms, the functional (GGA & hybrid, e.g. PBE and PBE0, BLYP and B3LYP), the cell size of the QM region, and the basis set, to distinguish the role of each in performance and parallel scaling bottlenecks.

Name	Functional	QM cell size	Basis set	QM atoms	Total atoms
MQAE-BLYP	BLYP	14 x 17 x 11	MOLOPT	34	~16k
MQAE-B3LYP	B3LYP		EMSL		
MQAE-B3LYP-large		28 x 34 x 22			
CBD_PHY-PBE	PBE	25 x 25 x 25	MOLOPT	68	~168k
CBD_PHY-PBE0	PBE0		HFX		
CIC-19-BLYP	BLYP	18 x 18 x 18	MOLOPT	19	~150k
CIC-253-BLYP	BLYP	27 x 25 x 25	MOLOPT	253	
CIC-253-B3LYP	B3LYP		EMSL		

Figure 1: Overview of the BioExcel QM/MM benchmarks reported on in this document

Machines

Cirrus@EPCC (HPE SGI ICE XA):

- CPU compute nodes:
 - 2 x 18-core Intel Xeon (Broadwell) E5-2695, 2.1 GHz
 - 256GB RAM
- GPU compute nodes:
 - 2 x NVIDIA Tesla V100 (Volta) SXM2-16GB
 - 2 x 20-core Intel Xeon (Cascade Lake) Gold 6248, 2.4 GHz
 - 384GB RAM
- Infiniband

ARCHER2@EPCC (HPE CRAY EX):

- Compute nodes:
 - 2 x 64-core AMD EPYC (Zen2 Rome) 7742, 2.25GHz
 - 256GB RAM
- HPE Cray Slingshot

Results on Cirrus CPU nodes are for CP2K release version 8.1, whilst results on Cirrus GPU nodes and ARCHER2 are with CP2K version 8.2.

Benchmarking & analysis protocol - interpreting these results

Benchmarking protocol

Multiple - usually 5 - repeated runs to rule out machine variability were performed for each benchmark on each machine for both 1 MD step and 6 MD steps.

Total times and speedups

Total times and derived speedups plotted here reflect per-MD-step average times computed by in each case subtracting the repeated-run-average for 1 MD step from the corresponding average for 6 MD steps to factor out the cost of initialisation and first MD step, after which per-MD-step averages were computed over the remaining 5 intervening MD steps (2-6).

Top subroutines by rank-average self time

To highlight bottlenecks to scaling, the subroutines with the top n largest per-MD-step rank-average self times computed as described above are shown by plotting for each number of cores a stacked bar showing the sizes of those subroutines' fractional contribution to total execution time at that scale. Since fractional rather than absolute subroutine times are shown, care should be taken not to draw any direct conclusions regarding the speedup of individual subroutines.

Load imbalances

Load imbalances for subroutines were computed using per-MD-step averages of the rank-max and rank-average self times arrived at following above protocol, and plotted as $(\text{max/ave} - 1.0)$, i.e. their deviation from perfect balance, so that a subroutine with perfect balance ($\text{max/ave} == 1$) has zero visual contribution in a stacked bar representing load imbalances of multiple subroutines whereas a subroutine with e.g. 40% imbalance ($\text{max/ave} = 1.4$) reads as 0.4 and can easily be compared with imbalances of other subroutines.

Cirrus CPU results

MQAE with BLYP on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 2: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 3: total CP2K speedup

Figure 4: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 5: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

MQAE with BLYP on Cirrus CPU scaling summary

- top 10 subroutines by ave self time cover 60%-70% of runtime
- QM/MM
 - qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG **not significant**
 - qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG **not significant**
 - qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G shrinks, **small significance**
 - qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G shrinks, **small significance**
- PW
 - pw_integral_ab and other pw_ grow, **significant**
- MPI
 - mp_* **very significant**
- FFT
 - shrinks to **small significance**
- Misc.
 -

MQAE with B3LYP on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

(b) 6 threads

Figure 6: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 6 threads

Figure 7: total CP2K speedup

(a) 1 thread

(b) 6 threads

Figure 8: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 6 threads

Figure 9: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

MQAE with B3LYP on Cirrus CPU scaling summary

- top 10 subroutines by ave self time cover 70%-80% of runtime
- HFX integrals & derivatives
 - derivatives_four_center_bin contribution does not scale well, **very significant**
 - integrate_four_center_bin does not scale well, **very significant**
- QM/MM
 - qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG **not significant**
 - qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG **not significant**
 - qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G **not significant**
 - qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G **small significance**
- PW
 - pw_integral_ab grows, **significant**
- MPI
 - mp_* **significant**
- FFT
 - shrinks, **not significant**
- Misc.
 -

MQAE with B3LYP, larger cell size (8x volume) on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

Figure 10: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

Figure 11: total CP2K speedup

(a) 1 thread

Figure 12: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 1 thread

Figure 13: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 14: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 15: total CP2K speedup

Figure 16: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 17: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE on Cirrus CPU scaling summary

- top 10 subroutines by ave self time cover 75%-80% of runtime
- QM/MM
 - qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG: contribution shrinks but **significant**, minor load imbalance
 - qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG: contribution shrinks but **significant**, minor load imbalance
 - qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G: mostly **not significant** except somewhat for higher threadcounts (6), minor load imbalance
 - qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G: **not significant**, minor load imbalance
- PW
 - pw_integral_ab contribution **grow (!)** to **significant** fraction, minor load imbalance
 - pw_restrict_s3, pw_prolongate contributions also grow with scale, but remain **relatively insignificant** overall (most significant for pure MPI runs)
- MPI
 - mp_* contributions appearing in top subroutines grow to **significant** (>20%), some load imbalance
- FFT
 - fft3d_ps contribution constant or shrinking, **not significant**, load imbalance minor but growing

CBD_PHY with PBE0 on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

Figure 18: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

Figure 19: total CP2K speedup

- cp_fm_write_unformatted
- derivatives_four_center_bin
- fft3d_ps
- fft_wrap_pw1pw2_200
- integrate_four_center_bin
- mp_alloall_222v
- mp_sum_dm3
- mp_sum_lv
- mp_waitany
- pw_integral_sb
- pw_prolongate_s3
- pw_restrict_s3
- qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG
- qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G
- qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG

(a) 1 thread

Figure 20: top 10 subroutines by average self time

- cp_fm_write_unformatted
- derivatives_four_center_bin
- fft3d_ps
- fft_wrap_pw1pw2_200
- integrate_four_center_bin
- mp_alloall_222v
- mp_sum_dm3
- mp_sum_lv
- mp_waitany
- pw_integral_sb
- pw_prolongate_s3
- pw_restrict_s3
- qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG
- qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G
- qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG

(a) 1 thread

Figure 21: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE0 scaling summary

- top 10 subroutines by ave self time cover 80%-90% of runtime
- HFX integrals & derivatives
 - `derivatives_four_center_bin` contribution does not scale well, **very significant**
 - `integrate_four_center_bin` does not scale well, **significant**
- QM/MM
 - `qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG` contribution shrinks to **small significance**, minor but growing load imbalance
 - `qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG` contribution shrinks but still **somewhat significant**, minor load imbalance
 - `qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G` **not significant**
 - `qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G` **not significant**
- PW
 - `pw_integral_ab` contribution grows (!) to **somewhat significant**, minor growing load imbalance
 - `pw_restrict` and `pw_prolongate` contributions grow to **somewhat significant**
- MPI
 - grow to **small significance**
- FFT
 - **not significant**
- Misc.
 - `cp_fm_write_unformatted` comes in at largest scale

CIC-19 with BLYP on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 22: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 23: total CP2K speedup

Figure 24: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 25: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-19 with BLYP on Cirrus CPU scaling summary

- top 10 subroutines by ave self time cover 70%-80% of runtime
- QM/MM
 - qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG contribution shrinks but still **significant**, minor load imbalance
 - qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG contribution shrinks but still **very significant**, minor load imbalance
 - qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G **small significance**
 - qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G **small significance**
- PW
 - pw_integral_ab grows (!) to become **significant**, negligible load imbalance
- MPI
 - mp_* total contribution (collective comms) **very significant**
- FFT
 - contribution shrinks to **not significant**
- Misc.
 - grid_collocate_task_list **small significance**

CIC-253 with BLYP on Cirrus CPU

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 26: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 27: total CP2K speedup

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 28: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 3 threads

(d) 6 threads

Figure 29: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-253 with BLYP on Cirrus CPU scaling summary

- top 10 subroutines by ave self time cover 80%-90% of runtime
- QM/MM
 - qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG **not significant**
 - qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG **small significance**
 - qmmm_elec_gaussian_low_G **significant** for higher threadcount, **small significance** otherwise
 - qmmm_forces_gaussian_low_G **small significance**
- PW
 - **not significant**
- MPI
 - mp_* **extremely significant**
- FFT
 - **not significant**
- Misc.
 -

Cirrus GPU results

MQAE with BLYP on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 threads

Figure 30: total CP2K time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 31: total CP2K speedup

(a) 10 threads

Figure 32: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 33: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

MQAE with B3LYP on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 thread

Figure 34: total CP2K time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 35: total CP2K speedup

(a) 10 thread

Figure 36: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 37: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

MQAE with B3LYP, larger cell size (8x volume) on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 threads

Figure 38: total CP2K time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 39: total CP2K speedup

Fraction of total time per MD step

(a) 10 threads

Figure 40: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Load imbalance

(a) 10 threads

Figure 41: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 threads

Figure 42: total CP2K time

(a) 10 thread

Figure 43: total CP2K speedup

(a) 10 threads

Figure 44: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 1 thread

Figure 45: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE0 on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 threads

Figure 46: total CP2K time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 47: total CP2K speedup

(a) 10 threads

Figure 48: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 49: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-19 with BLYP on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 threads

Figure 50: total CP2K time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 51: total CP2K speedup

(a) 10 threads

Figure 52: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 53: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-253 with BLYP on Cirrus GPU

(a) 10 threads

Figure 54: total CP2K time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 55: total CP2K speedup

(a) 10 threads

Figure 56: top 10 subroutines by average self time

(a) 10 threads

Figure 57: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

ARCHER2 CPU results

MQAE with BLYP on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 58: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 59: total CP2K speedup

Figure 60: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 61: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

MQAE with B3LYP on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 62: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 63: total CP2K speedup

Figure 64: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 65: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

MQAE with B3LYP, larger cell size (8x volume) on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 66: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 67: total CP2K speedup

Figure 68: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 69: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 70: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 71: total CP2K speedup

Figure 72: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 73: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CBD_PHY with PBE0 on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 74: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 75: total CP2K speedup

Figure 76: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 77: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-19 with BLYP on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 78: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 79: total CP2K speedup

Figure 80: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 81: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-253 with BLYP on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 82: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 83: total CP2K speedup

Figure 84: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 85: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines

CIC-253 with B3LYP on ARCHER2

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 86: total CP2K time

(a) 1 thread

(b) 2 threads

(c) 4 threads

(d) 8 threads

Figure 87: total CP2K speedup

Figure 88: top 10 subroutines by average self time

Figure 89: load imbalances of top 10 subroutines